

Annex to: Update of the risk assessment of mineral oil hydrocarbons in food.
doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2023.8215

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Annex A – Known sources of mineral oil hydrocarbons present in food

The list of known sources is long, and probably still incomplete. Some uses encountered in the past should have been phased out, but are nonetheless reported here, since they may not have fully disappeared and may help understanding sources not identified so far. They also illustrate the wide range of possible sources of MOH contamination in foods.

Most work on identifying sources occurred between 1990 and about 2005. It was carried out by the Kantonales Labor Zürich. Being an official food control authority, not all findings were published (here referred to as unpublished results), and, as mentioned in the main text, wherever possible, measures were taken to reduce the contamination. However, this was in Switzerland and it is unknown what happened in other European countries.

A.1. Environmental contamination

MOH from the atmosphere

The principal atmospheric contaminants containing MOH are exhaust gases from vehicles, e.g. unburned fuel and lubricating oil, unburned heating oils (soot) as well as debris from tyres and road bitumen. Plants are contaminated with MOH from the atmosphere through absorption from the gas phase (volatile compounds eluted from GC with a retention time up to approximately n-C24) and deposition of particulate matter (MOH beyond about n-C16). The first is an equilibration process, the latter depends on the deposition and retention of dust on the plant surface (e.g. stickiness) and the soil. The contamination of plants seems to occur predominantly by particulate matter, but it is unknown whether it is primarily by deposition onto the plant or into the soil, from which the plants takes it up. Soil contains MOSH, with particularly high concentrations in, e.g., rotting needles below pine trees and compost in which slowly degradable hydrocarbons are accumulated (Neukom et al., 2002).

Leaves from lettuce and a beech tree in the region of Zurich contained about 4 mg MOSH/kg dry mass (Neukom et al., 2002), ranging approximately from n-C16 to n-C40, centred on n-C25 – n-C26. This distribution corresponded to the MOH found in the particulate matter in the atmosphere and suggested that lubricating oil emitted from diesel engines and incomplete combustion of diesel or heating oil were the predominant source of the contamination. Cool diesel engines tend to emit unburned diesel oil, characterized by MOSH from n-C14 to n-C24, hot diesel engines primarily lubricating oil centred around n-C28 (Brandenberger et al., 2005).

In all investigated cases, the MOH almost entirely consisted of MOSH. Since the source MOH contain substantial proportions of MOAH, it is assumed that the MOAH are degraded, possibly by light. The reaction products are unknown.

The oil extracted from sunflower seeds manually picked from fields in the north eastern Switzerland contained 0.1-2.4 mg MOSH/kg, ranging from n-C20 to n-C36 and centred on n-C27, as typical for lubricating oils. The highest concentrations were found in the seeds from fields in the east suburbs of Zurich, probably reflecting the dominant westerly winds (Grundböck et al., 2010).

Milk fat usually contains around 10 mg MOSH/kg (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zürich) and might be largely from the environmental contamination of the feed for the cows.

In olive pomace (sansa) oil, usually 150-350 mg MOSH/kg are found (Moret et al., 2003). The origin has not been conclusively clarified, but might be from environmental MOH reconcentrated into the residual oil extracted from the pomace. Gharbi et al. (2017) compared the MOH in the oil extracted with solvent from Tunisian olives and the oils obtained from the same olives by physical means. The average MOSH concentration

in the solvent-extracted oil (11.1 mg/kg) was about four times higher than in oil extracted by physical means (2.6 mg/kg). This supports that the MOSH are mainly located in the waxy surface of the olives, from which they are poorly extracted by the oil during oil production by pression or centrifugation. Hence, they remain in the pomace and are only extracted by the subsequently applied stronger means, such as solvent. It remained unclear whether the MOSH were entirely from environmental origin. No MOAH were detected.

In grape seed oils, commonly 40-150 mg MOSH/kg were measured, for which it is unclear whether they are from the environment or pesticide formulations. It was shown that they are from the skins which are not completely removed from the kernels from which the oil is obtained (Fiorini et al., 2008).

For the toxicological evaluation of MOSH from the environment it should be taken into account that the constituents of most concern, those accumulated by humans, tend to be enriched in the environment (Grob, 2018). Partial, selective degradation by microorganisms in the soil, followed by selective degradation by plants and then by animals is likely to occur by the same mechanisms as in humans, leaving behind those hydrocarbons that humans have difficulty in metabolising. Hence concentrations in food of MOH being residues of such enriching processes cannot be directly compared to concentrations of MOH of original composition. MOH components in dairy products could be an example for which the concentration might seriously underestimate the risk when compared to animal experiments with complete mineral oil products. Since over 90% (probably over 95 %) of the MOSH are rapidly degraded, the re-concentration of the accumulating species may be more than an order of magnitude (Ebert et al., 1966; Barp et al., 2017).

Mineral oil hydrocarbons in marine and freshwater ecosystems

Little is known about the contamination of fish and seafood with MOH. Apart from accidents and other oil spills, potential sources are speculation. In freshwater fish from populated regions, the sources could include dust washed into the water or debris/extracts from tyres and road tar.

Forty samples of fish from sea and fresh water contained 20-800 mg MOSH/kg in the fat, with molecular mass distributions centred between n-C17 and n-C28 (3-150 mg MOSH/kg related to the entire fish. None of the samples was from an area with a known oil spill. A trout containing 400 mg MOSH/kg fat was from a river in a remote area north-east of Zurich without housing and asphalt on roads (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich).

A.2. Food processing

Release agents

Up to the 1990s, release agents were probably the predominant source of MOH in food. Paraffin oils, typically centred on about n-C23, were used in large amounts by the bakery industry to spray surfaces of channels through which dough should slide, knives to cut the dough in portions or to cut freshly baked bread to slices. Mineral oil products were also used for wetting pans for baking bread and biscuits to ease the release of the final product (Grob et al., 1991a). Concentrations in the contaminated products were typically in the range of 500-3,000 mg/kg, with a maximum of 11,000 mg/kg found in biscuits. The same types of oils were used in industry working with sugar, such as candy manufacturers. No such use of MOH has been reported for many years.

De-dusting agents

Dust released during transport, pumping and storage of grain, soybeans or rice may form explosive mixtures. To bind the dust, the US-FDA authorised the use of white mineral oils for grain and rice with limits reaching 800 mg/kg in rice. Such practices were never authorised in Europe. Wheat flower from overseas regularly contained 2-4 mg MOSH/kg, but this is unlikely to be indicative of residues from de-dusting agents.

Machine oils

Harvesters were shown to contaminate sunflower seeds with diesel oil at up to 3 mg/kg and with lubricating oil at up to 5 mg/kg (Grundböck et al., 2010). These MOH largely end up in the extracted oil with reconcentration resulting in about a doubling of the concentration. It is assumed that this occurs not only in human foods, but also feeds.

At the collection station receiving the sunflower seeds from the farmers, one sample was further contaminated during drying with about 40 mg fuel or diesel oil/kg, another with 23 mg/kg (related to the extracted oil).

Heating occurred indirectly (Grundböck et al., 2010). The source of the contamination is unclear, but likely from exhaust sucked into the dryer from a tractor.

Oil mills use mineral oils for various purposes, the main applications probably being cleaning and maintenance of machinery. Levels of MOH in edible oils produced in large quantities were in the order of 10-30 mg/kg (Fiselier and Grob, 2009), the environmental contribution being part of it. In speciality oils, produced in smaller amounts, such as cold pressed oils or oils from special seeds, concentrations were frequently in the range of 100-1,000 mg/kg, maxima reaching about 3,000 mg/kg (Grob et al., 1994, Wagner et al. 2001; Moret et al., 2003). Producers indicated that they used white mineral oils. The molecular mass distribution was centred at n-C24 – n-C30.

After 2010, chocolate and cocoa products were still frequently contaminated with a broad variety of MOH, at levels usually below 10 mg/kg, but with maxima around 100 mg/kg. A contamination of 80 mg/kg, detected in 2010, could be traced back to milling of hazel nuts: mineral oil was used for machinery maintenance (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich).

Syringe-type dosing machinery (e.g. for dosing ice-cream into beakers) uses oils to lubricate the plunger. When the lubricating oil was applied at high pressure in order to prevent cream getting behind the plunger and cause microbial problems, there was a constant leakage of lubricating oil into the food. Rather than informing the person responsible for the process, the worker went to the pharmacy to buy Vaseline – which complicated the search for the source (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich).

There is a wide use of lubricating oils occasionally leaking into foods, such as in stirring units located above a paste or cream. However, amounts are commonly low, as the oil reservoirs are small.

Coating of foods

Up to about 1990, it was common practice to spray refined rice with mineral oil in order to render it shiny. Concentrations were usually in the range of 1,000 - 3,000 mg/kg. White oils were used with a molecular mass distribution centred on about n-C24. This practice has never been authorized and was stopped in Switzerland in 1989 by enforcement. However, in 2009, still a rice sample from Europe sprayed in the same way was found (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich).

It is widely believed that apples as well as other fruits and vegetables are regularly treated with mineral waxes for their preservation and to improve their appearance. According to EU legislation (see Section 1.3.5), microcrystalline waxes (E 905) are approved for coating of melons, papayas, mangos, and avocados, but application to these fruits does not seem frequent.

Some foods (primarily hard cheeses and sausages) are coated with a wax layer. For cheese it was shown that the migration into the 5 mm surface layer resulted in a concentration of 15 mg/kg; the wax was no longer detectable deeper in the cheese (Grob et al. 1991b). Castle et al. (1993b) found 10-150 mg/kg in the outermost 2 mm layer and calculated from <1 to 27 mg/kg for 20 samples of cheese.

Waxes from food contact materials

Mineral oil constituents may migrate from food contact materials (FCM), either by physical contact between with wetting foods (e.g. from plastics) or through the gas phase (evaporation and recondensation) into dry food. Waxed paper were used, e.g., for meat products, cheese, bakery ware or candies (Grob et al., 1991b; Castle et al., 1993). Concentrations in the foods strongly depend on the ratio of food contact surface per amount of food as well as on temperature (with high migration when contacting fat is molten). Waxed paperboard was used, e.g., to pack honey. Today these packaging materials are rarely encountered, but still large amounts of mineral waxes are used to render paperboard more water-resistant (Biedermann and Grob, 2010).

Migration from Plastics

Specified grades of MOH are approved as additives (e.g. internal lubricants) for the use in plastics for food contact according to Regulation (EU) No 10/2011, with or without restriction in use. Castle et al. (1991) investigated the migration from polystyrene and acrylonitrile/butadiene/styrene (ABS) containers containing up to 7-8 % MOH into aqueous simulants and various beverages. Migration was found to be below 0.5 mg/kg even for hot beverages, which can be attributed to the limited solubility of MOH in aqueous foods and the low diffusion out of the ABS polymer. Migrations between 1 and 5 mg/kg from polyolefins were found for fatty dry foods, like powdered formula for babies and cocoa powder (Biedermann-Brem and Grob, 2011).

Jute and sisal sacks

For manufacturing sacks (typically of around 1-1.5 kg weight for around 50 kg of content), jute and sisal fibres may be batched with about 7 % mineral oil to improve their spinning properties (Grob et al., 1991b). The volatile part of this oil (up to about n-C28, depending on temperature during storage) is transferred to the packed foods, primarily hazelnuts, cocoa beans, coconut meat, coffee, rice from Asia and oil seeds, typically at 10-100 mg/kg (Grob et al., 1991a, 1992, 1993; Moret et al., 1997). Bonvehi and Coll (2014) reported data on MOSH in cocoa butter from 2000 and 2001 with an average of 42 mg/kg if transported in jute bags.

In 1998, the Association of Chocolate, Biscuit and Confectionery Industries of Europe (Caobisco) together with the International Jute Organisation (IJO) established that the jute and sisal bags sent to Europe should be virtually free of mineral oil. In 2004, EFSA published an opinion on the use of mineral oil products for batching jute or sisal fibres for food contact sacks (EFSA 2004), but no related European regulation was established thereafter. Control by enforcement authorities indicate that sacks batched with MOH are no longer sent to Europe, but their use seems to be current for the transport from farmers to collection sites outside Europe. In fact, there is still a production and use of sacks with mineral batching oil in Asia and Africa.

Stauff et al. (2020) reported recent data on cocoa butter (n=142) with levels from <LOQ (2.5 mg/kg) to 162 mg/kg MOSH (sum of n-C10 – n-C50) and <LOQ to 55 mg/kg MOAH, but for most samples the concentrations were below the LOQ. The main target of their work was the removal of the MOH by deodorization, which is less efficient for cocoa butter than for other edible fats and oils owing to the limitation in heating to avoid transesterification of the triglycerides. Bonvehi and Coll (2014) had previously shown that MOSH up to n-C20 were fully eliminated by a deodorization process.

Lubricating oils for cans

Mineral oil products and waxes may be used in three parts of the can making process; (i) as sheet lubricants, (ii) as wax additives in can coatings and (iii) as a component of can sealing compounds.

Mineral oils are used to lubricate sheets of metal as they are cut and shaped into can bodies and ends. For two-piece drawn and wall ironed (DWI) cans (beverage and some food cans), residual lubricant is washed off before the coating is sprayed onto the can interior (Hill, 2007).

For two-piece draw redraw (DRD) cans, for the body of three-piece cans and for can ends (both classic and easy-open), the metal sheets are coated before cutting and forming. Hydrocarbon waxes or natural waxes, such as lanolin or carnauba wax, may be used as an additive in the coating to protect the coating as well as the tools and dies used during metal forming. These cans are either not washed before filling or are only rinsed with plain water (Stoker and Heinz, 2007).

Mineral oil products may also be used as components of the soft sealing compounds between the can body and the ends, where the metal pieces are curled together to make the hermetic can seal. It is generally considered that there is minimal contact between the sealing compound and the can contents.

Up to about 100 mg of oil or wax per square metre of metal is needed to provide adequate lubrication during can making. Assuming the smallest can with the highest

area to volume ratio (e.g. a small fish can) and that all oil or wax is retained in the can, the migration is expected to be around 18 mg/kg food. This upper estimate seems to be supported by the limited survey data available (Jickells et al. 1994; FSA 2003). Higher levels have been reported in canned oily foods, such as canned fish in oil. Concentrations in the oil were typically around 100 mg/kg and reached 820 mg/kg (Grob et al., 1997). However, these may have originated also from the oil or the fish before canning.

Printing inks

For paper and board, commonly offset printing inks containing 20-30 % mineral oil solvent are used. Drying occurs by setting, i.e. the solvent is sorbed into the fibres rather than evaporated. Due to the volatility of these MOH (typically centred on n-C17 - n-C19) they subsequently slowly evaporate. For the folding boxes, MOH evaporate either outwards into the atmosphere or inwards into the packed food (unless there is a functional barrier).

Up to about 2010, the use of mineral-oil-type solvents was standard also in food packaging. In 2010, a maximum of 210 mg MOH/kg was found in cocoa powder packed into a paper pouch that was in a fresh fibre paperboard box printed with MOH containing ink (Vollmer et al., 2011). However, afterwards "food grade" inks were used.

Recycled paper and board

Recycled paper and board contains MOH from, e.g., printing inks applied to newspaper and other heavily printed paper or board fed into the recycling process, adhesives, defoamers, solvents used as carriers for binders and waxes to improve water resistance (Biedermann and Grob, 2010; Biedermann et al., 2011). Since recycled board is not generally used for liquid food contact, migration is mostly limited to the components of sufficient volatility enabling transfer through the gas phase, which is up to about n-C24 at ambient temperature during extended periods of time (Lorenzini et al., 2010). Party plates may be an exception, since the surface layer usually consists of a polyolefin film that does not hinder the transfer into wetting food (Dima et al., 2011). Pizza boxes may be another exception, depending on the extent of wetting contact.

In 2010, 119 samples of dry foods intended for long term storage at ambient temperature from the German market were analyzed for MOH in the packaging materials (paperboard and internal bag) as well as the food (Vollmer et al., 2011). The mean MOSH concentration in 60 products packed in recycled board without an internal bag acting as a functional barrier was 10.9 mg/kg, the maximum 80 mg/kg. The MOAH mostly made up 10-20 % of the MOH and reached 6.1 mg/kg food. At the end of the shelf life or 16 months later, the average migration of the MOSH had increased to 14.3 mg/kg, with a maximum of 101 mg/kg (Biedermann et al., 2013). Migration into packs with internal plastic bags was lower or completely blocked, depending on the barrier properties of the plastic.

After storage during 9 months at ambient temperature, the MOSH migration into six test foods directly packed in folding boxes of recycled paperboard amounted to 65-80 % of the initial content in the paperboard, more than half of this during the first two months (Biedermann et al., 2013).

Later monitoring campaigns found clearly lower migration, as the subject had become a public issue (e.g. FSA, Information sheet n° 03/11).

Transport boxes are an important source of MOH migration, as this not only affects food in paperboard boxes, but also those in paper or plastic if the plastic has no effective barrier properties. Biedermann et al. (2011) showed this for a "high end" product of pasta packed in fresh fibre paper with a polypropylene window, then in a fresh fibre paperboard folding box that was wrapped into a polyethylene film of 20 µm thickness. Ten such boxes were packed into a transport box of corrugated board made of recycled material. Depending on the position of the packs in the transport box, migration through all these layers reached 6.1 and 2 mg MOSH and MOAH/kg pasta, respectively, after 65 days at ambient temperature (shelf life of 2 years).

Some of the foods packaged in paper and board, such as breakfast cereals and bakery ware, are consumed without further processing. Others, like rice or pasta, are cooked before consumption. It might be expected that most MOH are removed with steam distillation. However, experiments showed that boiling water removed only a minor part, probably because the water acted as a barrier hindering the MOH leaving the pores (Biedermann-Brem and Grob, 2011).

Adhesives

Some glues and adhesives contain MOH at up to 30 %. No data are available on the migration from bags, boxes and labels.

Antifoaming agents

MOH may be part of antifoaming agents in applications like pulping of paper and board or the washing of potato slices for chip/crisps manufacture. Up to 80 mg/kg were added to the wash water for the sliced potatoes.

Contamination in tanks and installations

The source of the contamination of the Ukrainian sunflower oil detected in 2008 with up to several percent of a base oil (Biedermann and Grob, 2009) has not been publicly confirmed, but according to a plausible hypothesis occurred by using tanks and installation also used for mineral oils products.

A.3. Pesticides

Some paraffin oils are allowed to be used as pesticides (see 1.3.5). They are applied to plants in order to suffocate pest organisms or can be used as co-formulants in plant protection products. No data are available on residues in food from this source.

A.4. Breast feeding

Breast milk (33 samples) was found to contain MOSH in the range of n-C15 – n-C45 at a mean concentration of 95 mg/kg fat and a maximum of 1,300 mg/kg (Noti et al., 2003). For the primiparous women and on the first days of breast feeding, typical concentrations were around 50 mg/kg fat. Continuing breast feeding mostly decreased it, but application of breast salves increased it. MOH from breast milk are another example of MOSH being enriched in accumulating constituents (MOH resisting degradation in the mothers' tissue being transferred to the baby).

Babies may also be exposed to mineral paraffins by direct licking off salves (often consisting of petroleum jelly) from the breast. Their worst case daily intake from breast care products was estimated to reach 40 mg/kg body weight (Noti et al., 2003).

MOSH in breast milk from 144 volunteers bearing children by caesarean section were analysed on days 4 and 20 after birth (Concin et al., 2008). The samples from day 4 contained virtually the same mixture of MOSH as the abdominal tissue fat of the mother, with concentrations ranging from 10 to 355 mg/kg fat (average, 44.6 mg/kg; median, 30 mg/kg). The fats from the day 20 milk contained <5-285 mg MOSH/kg (average, 21.7; median, 10 mg/kg), whereby almost all elevated concentrations were linked with a modified composition, suggesting a new source, such as use of breast salves.

1.1.1.1 Fat substitute

MOSH ("food-grade paraffin oils") have been recommended in weight-reducing diets as replacement of vegetable oil, e.g. in salad dressings. This practice was encouraged by 'best-selling' books dealing with weight-loss programs (e.g. Dukan, 2010).

1.1.1.2 MOH in animal feed

Parts of the mineral oils added to feeds are accumulated by animals and can be transferred to the human diet as meat, dairy products, fish or eggs. Their composition is likely to be changed towards those difficult for biotransformation, probably resulting in the enrichment of those most strongly accumulated by humans. Hence, at a given concentration they are expected to be of more concern than those of MOH directly ingested or used in the animal tests.

The predominantly applied physical refining of edible oils removes free fatty acids in the deodorization step and yields a condensate containing the free acids, some valuable components like tocopherols, but also most of the MOH below about n-C27 from the crude edible oils. Such condensates, in which 200-3000 mg MOSH/kg were measured (Wagner et al., 2001), are commonly used for the production of mixed animal feeds, possibly after extraction of some valuable components.

MOH were used as binders to facilitate homogeneous admixture of minor components in powder form to feeds, like minerals and vitamins (Grob et al., 2001). Concentrations in feeds typically ranged from 500-1000 mg/kg. In about 50 samples of eggs, the fat phase of the egg yolk contained on average about 30 mg MOSH/kg centred on n-C21 – n-C24, with a maximum of 80 mg/kg; nearly all eggs were contaminated (Grob et al., 2001 and surveillance data from the Official Food Control Zurich). The same source caused chicken, beef and pork meat to be contaminated. At least in Switzerland, this use of mineral oil products was stopped in the early years 2000.

In 1999, it was detected that spent edible oils, mainly frying oils, contaminated with mineral oil wastes, such as used motor oils, were added to feed as a source of lipids (Grob et al., 2001). The spent edible oils were collected at public recycling stations next to tanks for other liquid wastes, including surplus pesticide solutions, paints, diluents and used crankcase oil. Although the tanks were separated and clearly labelled, apparently wastes were poured into the wrong tank. Also oils collected at restaurants were sometimes severely contaminated with non-edible wastes. At least in Switzerland, the use of such spent edible oils for feeds was stopped shortly after this being detected.

Later, feeding of farmed animals other than fur animals with catering waste or feed material containing or derived from catering waste was prohibited under the EC Regulation 1774/2002.

Srbínovska et al. (2020) found no MOH in wild salmon and some other fish (<0.1 mg/kg), but up to 4.3 mg/kg MOSH in farmed salmon (totally 18 samples), for which MOH in the feed were assumed to be the source. MOAH were detected in 4 of 21 samples, with a maximum of 1.4 mg/kg. The authors mention unpublished findings by the same group of 3.7 and 221.5 mg MOSH/kg feed (average 27.2 mg/kg) in 19 samples from four rainbow trout breeding areas in Italy and MOSH residues in the fillets ranging from 0.3 to 6.9 mg/kg fresh weight (average 1.9 mg/kg).

A.5. Veterinary products

In animal pharmacy, MOH are often used as adjuvants in vaccines, for ointments, anti-dusting agents in medicated feeds, vehicles in anti-mastitic intra-mammary infusions, emollients in teat dips, ingredients in parasiticides, and vehicles in some subcutaneously-applied depot products (EMA, 1995). For hydrocarbons >n-C30 it is known that they are not absorbed in ruminants and have a laxative effect (RIKILT, 2008).

Bag palm largely consists of MOH. In an experiment applying an extra amount of bag palm followed by mechanical milking, no transfer to the milk was detected with a detection limit of about 5 mg/kg milk fat (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich). This did not exclude that transfer occurred more slowly, contaminating the milk in the subsequent milking.

A.6. Other sources

Analysing foods for MOH often revealed contamination that could not be related to the sources listed above. Tracing these tended to be labour-intensive and, if finally identified, revealed unexpected particular cases. Some examples: The quality manager of a producer may feel sure that no MOH are used in their processes, but finally detects that one of the workers struggling with a technical problem quietly solved it using an oil he obtained from a colleague in a mechanics shop or a pharmacy. Particularly products from pharmacies may seem acceptable to them.

Dry butter fat for cooking contained around 100 mg MOSH and/or POSH/kg. It was produced from butter returned from the sale as it had exceeded the shelf life for fresh butter. Instead of laborious unpacking, it was molten out of the packaging material and the warm butter fat extracted the packaging material (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich).

Mixed pralines came in fresh fiber packing with printing inks free of mineral oil. Nevertheless, they contained 30-80 mg MOH/kg, including some 20 % MOAH, as typically encountered in recycled paperboard. It turned out that the pralines were produced in batches and stored on large sheets of recycled paperboard (with a clean-appearing white surface layer) before being combined in a collection (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich).

One out of about twenty samples of fat tissue from pork (from totally about 250 samples mainly collected in a slaughter house) contained in the order of 200 mg MOH/kg ranging from n-C10 to n-C14 (unpublished data, Kantonales Labor Zurich). It turned out that a product sold as "manure conditioner", essentially consisting of MOH with herbs, was fed to sows in order to stop diarrhoea in piglets.

References

- Barp L, Biedermann M, Grob K, Blas-Y-Estrada F, Nygaard UC, Alexander J, Cravedi JP, 2017. Accumulation of mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH) in female Fischer 344 rats: Comparison with human data and consequences for risk assessment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 575, 1263–1278.
- Biedermann M and Grob K, 2009. How "white" was the mineral oil in the contaminated Ukrainian sunflower oils? *Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol.*, 111, 313–319.

- Biedermann M, Ingenhoff JE, Barbanera M, Garbini D, Grob K, 2011. Migration of mineral oil into noodles from recycled fibers in the paperboard box and the corrugated board transport box as well as from printing inks: a case study. *Packaging Technology and Science*, 24, 281–290.
- Biedermann M, Ingenhoff JE, Zurfluh M, Richter L, Simat T, Harling A, Altkofer W, Helling R, Grob K, 2013. Migration of mineral oil, photoinitiators and plasticisers from recycled paperboard into dry foods: a study under controlled conditions. *M Food Addit Contam A*, 30, 885-898.
- Biedermann M and Grob K, 2010. Is recycled newspaper suitable for food contact materials? Technical grade mineral oils from printing inks. *European Food Research and Technology*, 230(5):785-96.
- Biedermann-Brem S and Grob K, 2011. Removal of mineral oil migrated from paperboard packing during cooking of foods in boiling water. *Eur Food Res Technol*, 232, 1035–1041.
- Bonvehí J and Ventura Coll F, 2014. Mineral oil paraffins in jute bags and cocoa butter. *Acta Alimentaria*, 43(1):40-52.
- Brandenberger S, Mohr M, Grob K and Neukom HP, 2005. Contribution of unburned lubricating oil and diesel fuel to particulate emission from passenger cars *Atmospheric Environment*, 39, 6985-6994.
- Castle L, Kelly M, Gilbert J, 1991. Migration of mineral hydrocarbons into foods. 1. Polystyrene containers for hot and cold beverages. *Food Additives & Contaminants*, 8(6):693-9.
- Castle L, Kelly M, Gilbert J, 1993. Migration of mineral hydrocarbons into foods. 2. Polystyrene, ABS, and waxed paperboard containers for dairy products. *Food Additives & Contaminants*, 10(2):167-74.
- Concin N, Hofstetter G, Plattner B, Tomovski C, Fiselier K, Gerritzen K, Fessler S, Windbichler G, Zeimet A, Ulmer H, Siegl H, Rieger K, Concin H and Grob K, 2008. Mineral oil paraffins in human body fat and milk. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 46, 544-552.
- Dima G, Verzera A and Grob K, 2011. Migration of mineral oil from party plates of recycled paperboard into foods: 1. is recycled paperboard fit for the purpose? 2. adequate testing procedure. *Food Additives Contaminants*, 28, 1619–1628.
- Dukan P, 2010. *The Dukan Diet*. Ed. Hodder & Stoughton Ltd.
- Ebert AG, Schleifer CR, Hess SM, 1966. Absorption, disposition, and excretion of tritium-mineral oil in rats. *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 9, 923–929.
- EFSA Journal (2004). Opinion of the Scientific Panel on Food Additives, Flavourings, Processing Aids and Materials in Contact with Food (AFC) on a request from the Commission related the use of mineral oils in jute and sisal bags. Question No EFSA-Q-2003-072.
- EMA (The European Agency for the Evaluation of Medicinal Products), 1995. The European Agency for the Evaluation of Medicinal Products. Committee for Veterinary medicinal Products. Mineral hydrocarbons – Summary Report. EMEA/CVMP/069/95-FINAL. Available from http://www.ema.europa.eu/docs/en_GB/document_library/Maximum_Residue_Limits_-_Report/2009/11/WC500015093.pdf.
- Fiorini D, Fiselier K, Biedermann M, Ballini R, Coni E, and Grob K, 2008. Contamination of grape seed oil with mineral oil paraffins *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 58, 11245-11250.
- Fiselier K and Grob K, 2009. Determination of mineral oil paraffins in foods by on-line HPLC–GC–FID: lowered detection limit; contamination of sunflower seeds and oils. *European Food Research and Technology*, 229(4):679-88.
- FSA (Food Standards Agency), 2003. Mineral hydrocarbons in food contact materials. Food Survey Information Sheet Number 34/03. 29th January 2003. Available from <http://www.food.gov.uk/science/surveillance/fsis2003/34fcm>.
- Gharbi I, Moret S, Chaari O, Issaoui M, Conte LS, Lucci P, Hammami M, 2017. Evaluation of hydrocarbon contaminants in olives and virgin olive oils from Tunisia. *Food Control.*, 75:160-6.
- Grob K, Artho A, Biedermann M and Mikle H, 1993. Contamination of hazel nuts and chocolate by mineral oil from jute and sisal bags. *Zeitschrift fur Lebensmittel-Untersuchung und -Forschung*, 197, 370-374.

- Grob K, Biedermann M, and Bronz M, 1994. Resultate einer Kontrolle von Speiseölen: Fälschungen durch Zumischungen, Verunreinigungen Mitt. Gebiete Lebensm. Hyg., 85, 351-365.
- Grob K, Biedermann M, Artho A, and Egli J, 1991a. Food Contamination by Hydrocarbons from Packaging Materials Determined by Coupled LC-GC. Lebensm. Unters. Forsch., 193, 213-219.
- Grob K, Huber M, Boderius U, and Bronz M, 1997. Mineral Oil Material in Canned Foods. Food Additives and Contaminants, 14, 83-88.
- Grob K, Lanfranchi M, Egli J, and Artho A, 1991b. Determination of food contamination by mineral oil from jute bags using coupled LC-GC. AOAC, 74, 506-512.
- Grob K, 2018. Toxicological assessment of mineral hydrocarbons in foods: state of present discussions. Perspective J. Agric. Food Chem., 66, 6968-6974.
- Grob K, Vass M, Biedermann M and Neukom HP, 2001. Contamination of animal feed and food from animal origin with mineral oil hydrocarbons. Food Additives and Contaminants, 18, 1-10.
- Grundböck F, Fiselier K, Schmid F, Grob K, 2010. Mineral oil in sunflower seeds: the sources. Eur. Food Res. Technol. 231, 209–213.
- Jickells SM, Nichol J and Castle L, 1994. Migration of mineral hydrocarbons into foods .6. Press lubricants used in food and beverage cans. Food Additives and Contaminants, 11, 595-604.
- Lorenzini R, Fiselier K, Biedermann M, Barbanera M, Braschi I and Grob K, 2010. Saturated and aromatic mineral oil hydrocarbons from paperboard food packaging: Prediction of long-term migration from contents in the paperboard; data from the market. Food Additives and Contaminants, Part A, 27, 1765-1774.
- Moret S, Grob K and Conte LS, 1997. Mineral oil polyaromatic hydrocarbons in foods, eg from jute bags, by on-line LC-solvent evaporation (SE)-LC-GC-FID. Zeitschrift Fur LebensmittelUntersuchung Und-Forschung a-Food Research and Technology, 204, 241-246
- Moret S, Populin T, Conte LS, Grob K and Neukom HP, 2003. Occurrence of C15-C45 mineral paraffins in olives and olive oils. Food Additives and Contaminants, 20, 417-426.
- Neukom HP, Grob K, Biedermann M, Noti A, 2002. Food contamination by C20-C50 mineral paraffins from the atmosphere. Atmospheric Environment, 36, 4839-4847.
- Noti A, Grob K, Biedermann M, Deiss U, Brüscheweiler BJ, 2003. Exposure of babies to C15-C45 mineral paraffins from human milk and breast salves. Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology, 38, 317-325.
- RIKILT, 2008. Bulder AS, Hoogenboom LAP, Kan CA (ASG), van Raamsdonk LVD, Traag WA, Bouwmeester H. Risk assessment of Nickel, Mineral Oils, Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Volatile Organic Compounds in animal feed materials. Report 2007.020, 1-102.
- Srbínovska A, Conchione C, Lucci P, Moret S, 2020. On-Line HP(LC)-GC-FID Determination of Hydrocarbon Contaminants in Fresh and Packaged Fish and Fish Products. Journal of AOAC INTERNATIONAL, 1–7.
- Stauff A, Schnapka J, Heckel F, Matissek R, 2020. Mineral Oil Hydrocarbons (MOSH/MOAH) in Edible Oils and Possible Minimization by Deodorization Through the Example of Cocoa Butter. Eur. J. Lipid Sci. Technol., 122.
- Stocker J and Heinz HJ, 2007. new technologies and chemistries for food can coatings. New Food, 10(3):46.
- Vollmer A, Biedermann M, Grundböck F, Ingenhoff JE, Biedermann-Brem S, Altkofer W, Grob K, 2011. Migration of mineral oil from printed paperboard into dry foods: survey of the German market. Eur Food Res Technol, 232, 175–182.
- Wagner C, Neukom HP, Grob K, Moret S, Populin T, and Conte LS, 2001. Mineral paraffins in vegetable oils and refinery by-products for animal feeds. Mitt. Lebensm. Hyg., 92, 499-514.